

Optimization-based design of insulating cementitious foams combined with phase change materials for NZEBs

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ABSTRACT: This work aims to introduce a new multiobjective optimization method for designing insulating cementitious foams combined with phase change materials (PCMs) to improve the energy performance of buildings. To achieve this, the multiobjective Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) and EnergyPlus software are dynamically coupled. Parametric models for PCMs and insulating cementitious foams are implemented in EnergyPlus to optimize their thickness and the PCM melting temperature. The BESTEST 900 from ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 140-2011 is chosen as a case study to evaluate the performance of the different designs. As objective functions, the annual heating and cooling loads are calculated in Sofia city, Bulgaria-EU. The results reveal several conclusions in terms of physics correlations between the design variables and objective functions. Regarding the total annual loads, the best design reduces 8.95% of the loads (compared to the Baseline model) by using 10 cm of cementitious foam combined with 2.5 cm of PCM with a melting temperature of 24.41 °C.

KEYWORDS: Energy conservation, Insulating cementitious foam, Phase change material, Multiobjective optimization, Building performance simulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Developing new building materials is a key research area to reduce the energy consumption in buildings and related CO₂ emissions. Researchers have conducted major efforts for developing two main types of materials regarding their application in buildings: insulating materials and energy storage materials.

Insulating materials are useful for reducing the thermal transmittance of building envelopes and controlling their heat loss and/or heat gain [1]. Typical insulating materials such as polyisocyanurates, extruded and expanded polystyrenes, and mineral and rock wools can achieve a very low thermal conductivity. However, most of these materials are highly flammable and have low recyclability. Thus, cementitious foams have great potential as insulating materials because of their low thermal conductivity, and their advantages of being non-flammable, non-toxic, and fully recyclable.

Moreover, energy storage materials can accumulate excess heat from indoor air and can be used to cool buildings efficiently. In particular, phase change materials (PCMs) have attracted great attention from the construction sector to improve the energy efficiency of buildings [2]. While undergoing their phase transition, PCMs can store and release large amounts of heat energy and have a stabilizing thermal effect inside buildings [3]. Despite its enormous energy-saving potential,

successful use of passive PCM-based systems in buildings is not implicitly guaranteed. This is because the performance of passive PCMs strongly depends on their complete daily thermal cycles [4].

Within this context, the NRG-STORAGE project [7] proposes a new cementitious foam with embedded micro-encapsulated PCM, so-called NRG-FOAM, aiming to achieve a lightweight material with an advanced insulation property and enhanced heat storage capacity.

Although the thermal properties of new materials can be measured using proper laboratory experiments, their real performances and optimum design have to be carried out at the building scale. Advanced building performance simulation tools are a suitable method to achieve it, which can predict the performance of the new materials in the built environment while considering real local climate conditions [5].

In this first effort, a multiobjective optimization method is proposed to find the optimal designs of insulating cementitious foams combined with PCMs in buildings. To achieve this, the multiobjective Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) and EnergyPlus software are dynamically coupled. As a case study, the BESTEST 900 is chosen to evaluate the annual heating and cooling performances of the different feasible designs.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Case study

The ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 140-2011 BESTEST 900 is employed to evaluate the performance of several foam-PCM designs applied to a typical wall structure [6]. The BESTEST is a basic test for building energy simulations, consisting of a single thermal zone with no interior partitions and two South-facing windows, see Fig. 1a. To characterize the performance of this building, the BESTEST 900 has an ideal HVAC system, whose thermostat control is set to 20 °C as the lower limit for heating and 27 °C as the upper limit for cooling.

Three real-scale BESTEST 900 buildings are currently under construction in Sofia, Bulgaria. These are demo prototypes that will be used to experimentally measure the performance of several NRG-FOAMS, developed within the NRG-STORAGE project [7]. So, a numerical model of this real scale BESTEST 900 is implemented in EnergyPlus 9.0 following the characteristics detailed in [6].

Figure 1:

Case study building. (a) BESTEST 900; (b) Prototypes under construction in Sofia (With courtesy of GBS Bulgaria).

2.2 Multi-objective optimization approach

Mathematically, the building performance optimization is posed as the following bi-objective optimization problem,

$$\text{Minimize } [f_1(x), f_2(x)], \quad (1)$$

where $x = [d_1, T_{\text{peak}}, d_2]$, being d_1 the thickness (m) of the PCM, T_{peak} the peak melting temperature (°C) of the PCM, and d_2 thickness (m) of the cementitious insulating foam. The objectives $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ are annual heating and cooling loads obtained as a result of the EnergyPlus simulations for the recent typical

meteorological year (TMYx.2004-2018¹) in Sofia, respectively.

2.3 Description of thermophysical properties of materials and design variables

Fig. 2 shows schematically the configuration of the wall construction for the Baseline model and the proposed one. The position of the PCM and the cementitious insulating foam among the wall layers can be observed in Fig. 2b.

Concrete foams (see Fig. 3) are made of cement paste (or sometimes mortar) in which a very high amount of air voids is entrapped by using an appropriate foaming agent. Cementitious foams are non-flammable, possess an extremely high flowability (also suitable for 3D printing), a very low specific weight, generally contain no aggregates, and have outstanding thermal insulation properties. Based on a proper mix design, a wide range of densities can be attained (varying from 90 to 300 kg/m³), as well as different porosities with particular pore size distributions.

Figure 2: Wall construction material configuration. (a) Baseline model; (b) Proposed wall.

¹ see data available in <http://climate.onebuilding.org/>

The thermophysical properties of the cementitious foam are taken from [8]. This foam was designed with a targeted dry density of 180 kg/m^3 while using a water-to-cement ratio for the cement paste of 0.4.

Figure 3:
Typical concrete foam and 3D heat flow schematization.

The Rubitherm RT25HC [9] is chosen as reference PCM. With this, a shift of $+10/-10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is numerically allowed for the enthalpy curve (latent capacity) of the material to study the optimal melting temperature (T_{peak}) in the optimization task, see Fig. 4. The latent thermal capacity of PCM is represented by the PCM model (*MaterialProperty:PhaseChange*) of EnergyPlus [10]. The main input in this model is the enthalpy-temperature curve of the PCM.

Figure 4:
Enthalpy curve of the PCM as a function of the temperature and the considered optimization range.

Tables 1 and 2 show the thermophysical properties of the wall construction layers for the Baseline model and the ones proposed herein, respectively. The optimization ranges for the cementitious foam and the PCM thicknesses are also specified in Table 2.

Table 1:
Thermo-physical properties of the wall construction elements for the Baseline model.

Elem.	K [W/(m K)]	Thickness [m]	Density [kg/m ³]	Cp [J/(kg K)]
Concr. Block	0.51	0.1000	1400	1000
Foam Insul.	0.04	0.0615	10	1400
Wood Siding	0.14	0.009	530	900

Table 2:
Thermo-physical properties of the wall construction elements for the proposed optimization.

Elem.	k [W/(m K)]	Thickness [m]	Density [kg/m ³]	Cp [J/(kg K)]
PCM RT25HC	0.200	0.001- 0.025	820	2000 (sens.) 1000
Concr. Block	0.510	0.100	1400	1000
Cement Foam	0.059	0.010- 0.100	180	938
Wood Siding	0.14	0.009	530	900

2.4 Implementation and setup of the optimization

To solve the optimization problem (1) for the case study, the NSGA-II optimization algorithm [11] is dynamically coupled with EnergyPlus to find the optimal design parameters that minimize both the heating and cooling loads. The implementation of the optimization algorithm is described in detail, in our previous work [12]. The optimization problem is solved by using a population size of 48 individuals and 100 generations, resulting in 4800 EnergyPlus simulations.

3. RESULTS

Fig. 5 shows the multiobjective optimization results obtained for the mentioned BESTEST 900 case study. These include the best trade-off (Pareto front) between heating and cooling loads and all the feasible designs evaluated during the optimization. Furthermore, the heating and cooling loads demanded by the Baseline model are also shown to have a reference for the improvements reached by the optimized designs.

From these results, it can be seen that there is a wide range of designs for the variables analyzed. In this space, several designs can reduce the cooling loads but increase the heating ones in comparison to the Baseline configuration. Moreover, there are a few designs that reduce the loads for both heating and cooling compared to the Baseline model.

Figure 5: Optimization results of the annual ideal loads, for heating and cooling, considering the case study in Sofia.

To better understand the physics behind the optimal designs (Pareto front), the optimum thicknesses of the cementitious foam and PCM are shown in Fig. 6. The designs go over the Pareto front from the solution with the best performance for heating (Opt-1) to the solution with the best performance for cooling (Opt-48). It can be observed that the thickness of the cementitious foam (insulation material) is the thickest one allowed (10 cm) to reduce the heating loads (Opt-1), and from here, it decreased until reaching the thinnest one allowed (1 cm) for minimizing the cooling loads (Opt-48). Moreover, all optimized designs chose the thickest PCM.

Figure 6: Optimal thicknesses for the cementitious foam and PCM for each design on the Pareto front.

Regarding the optimum melting temperature of the PCM, Fig. 7 shows the optimum T_{peak} obtained for each design on the Pareto front (Opt-1 to Opt-48). The design with the best performance for heating (Opt-1) employs a PCM with a peak melting temperature of 22.66 °C, while after that, the optimum T_{peak} increases up to 28 °C and stays around this value for reducing the cooling loads.

Figure 7: Optimized T_{peak} of the PCM obtained for each design on the Pareto front.

To enable quantitative analysis, Table 3 summarizes the performance of obtained optimum designs and their relative energy savings in comparison to the Baseline model. The configuration of these optimized designs is described as well.

The best design for reducing the heating loads (Opt-1), achieves 11.76% of heating savings but almost did not reduce the cooling loads (0.06%), resulting in an 8.73% saving on the total loads. Conversely, Opt-48 achieves a 30.01% of reduction for cooling but had increased heating loads by 89.38%, resulting in a 58.47% increase in the total loads. Regarding the best design for reducing the total loads, the Opt-4 is the best option on the Pareto front. This design achieves a reduction of 8.95% for the total loads by saving 11.34% and 2.14% for the heating and cooling loads, respectively. The configuration of this design comprises 10 cm thickness for the cementitious foam combined with 2.5 cm of PCM, and this PCM has a T_{peak} of 24.41 °C.

Table 2: Configuration and energy performance of the Baseline and optimized designs.

	Baseline	Opt-1	Opt-4	Opt-48
Heating load [kWh]	2914.14	2571.34	2583.8	5518.74
Cooling load [kWh]	1018.04	1017.46	996.28	712.51
Total load [kWh]	3932.18	3588.80	3580.0	6231.25
Heating saving [%]	-	11.76	11.34	-89.38
Cooling saving [%]	-	0.06	2.14	30.01
Total saving [%]	-	8.73	8.95	-58.47
d_1 [m]	-	0.025	0.025	0.025
T_{peak} [°C]	-	22.67	24.41	27.97
d_2 [m]	-	0.10	0.10	0.01

4. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a multiobjective methodology to optimize the design of an insulating cementitious foam combined with phase change material (PCM) in buildings. To address this, the multi-objective Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) was dynamically coupled with annual EnergyPlus simulations for the BESTEST 900 from ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 140-2011. Parametric models for the cementitious foam and PCM were implemented in the EnergyPlus simulations to study the optimal thicknesses of the materials along with the PCM melting temperatures.

The optimization results showed that heating and cooling loads have a complex and contradictory relationship regarding the design variables. Therefore, a simulation-based and multiobjective-based optimization approach is needed and highly recommended for performing the optimization of the PCM melting temperatures as well as of the insulation thickness in buildings.

Regarding the cementitious insulating foam, the optimum design for reducing heating loads is achieved for a thickness of 10 cm, while a thickness of 1 cm is necessary to minimize the cooling loads. This latter shows that insulation materials have to be carefully designed by also considering the building typology and local climate.

As for the PCM, all optimum solutions on the Pareto front employ the thickest option of 2.5 cm but were combined with different melting temperatures related to the performance of the design. A melting temperature of 22.66 °C was necessary for reducing the heating loads while a melting temperature of around 28 °C was preferred for reducing the cooling loads.

Regarding the optimal combination of the design variables, there is a design that can reduce the heating loads up to 11.76% and another design that can reduce the cooling loads up to 30%. In terms of total loads, the best design reduced 8.95% of the loads by using 10 cm of cementitious foam combined with 2.5 cm of PCM with a melting temperature of 24.41 °C. Here, it was demonstrated that it is possible to improve the original wall configuration by the optimum combination of a cementitious foam with a PCM. It may be worth noting that an improved performance compared to the original results was achieved by an increased thickness of the cementitious foam. This is because the building typology was dominated by heating loads and the original insulation had a lower thermal conductivity than the employed cementitious foam.

Finally, the proposed methodology showed great robustness to explore the optimum solutions for optimized building designs that use PCMs. Future works will be focused on adapting and employing the

methodology to design the NRG-FOAMs panels planned to be tested at a real scale BESTEST 900 buildings of the NRG-STORAGE project.

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